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Analysis of News Item Text Found In “Antara News” Entitled: “Indonesian Police Re-Examine ‘plastic’ rice”

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Abstrak

Antara news adalah koran harian yang berorientasi meliputi beberapa hal yang ada didalamnya seperti headline, editorial, artikel, opini, dunia, dan lain-lain. Tulisan ini bertujuan untuk menganalisa news item text pada harian Antara News yang berjudul “*Indonesian Police Re-Examine ‘plastic’ rice*”. Penelitian ini adalah berita yang diambil dari Antara News online yang dipublikasikan pada tanggal 26 Mei 2015, pukul 15:56:55. Dalam penelitian ini, penulis bersangkutan pada tata bahasa fungsional, terutama pada makna ideasional. Dalam rangka untuk mendapatkan tujuan penelitian ini, penulis menggunakan beberapa teori yang berkaitan dengan sastra, wacana, genre, tata bahasa dan makna ideasional itu sendiri. Dalam analisis tipe proses, ada empat jenis proses yang ditemukan dalam berita dan proses yang paling muncul adalah proses material. Proses Penulis juga menemukan bahwa ada berita genre; recount, yang mendominasi teks itu. Recount atau past tense itu mengembangkan teks tersebut

Kata Kunci : *Genre, Analisis Teks, News Paper*

Abstract

Antara News is one of the daily English newspaper which is oriented in some various field such as headline, editorial, article, opinion, world and etc. This paper aims to analyse the news item text in Antara News entitled “Indonesian Police Re-Examine ‘plastic’ rice”. The object of this study is news taken from Antara News online published on 26th of may 2015, 15:56:55 pm. In this study, the writer concerned on functional grammar, mainly on ideational meaning. In order to get the objective of this study, the writer used some theories related to the literature, discourse, genre, grammar and ideational meaning itself. In the Process type analysis, there were four types of processes found in the news and the most process appeared was material process. The writer also found that there was news item genre, instead of recount, which dominate the text . the recount or past tense develop the text

Keywords : *Genre, Text Analysis, News Paper*

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INTRODUCTION.

Language is a system of sounds and words to express one’s personal reactions, emotions and thoughts as well as to share information in daily social life. Language is meaningful, when the meaning is conveyed through language, people use language to interact and establish relations, to influence their behavior and express their expressions of the word. Article is one of the reading materials and usually deals with a particular issues or topic to give information of interest; in daily newspaper such as Antara News, The Jakarta Post, and Radar Tegal, etc. Antara News is one of the daily English newspaper which is oriented in some various field such as headline, editorial, article, opinion, world and etc. It shows that it is very interesting to analyze the article, especially the article in Antara News. This can be analyzed in the perspective of linguistic studies using the systemic functional linguistic theory. It includes analysis of mood structure, analysis of transitivity, analysis of theme-rheme, analysis of logical relationship and analysis of ideology.

According to Halliday’s theory, Forms of transitivity, like processes, participants, and the circumstances, happen in the clauses and sentences of a text. He states that “transitivity is the set of options by the speaker signs his or her experience and transitivity is really the base or fundamental of the semantic organization of experience”. Transitivity analyses are just a few among many, but

they are fundamental examples of how language patterns, especially transitivity, can bring the meaning and ideology of a literary text. They also rise further dimensions that proved more useful in stylistic analysis. The functional grammar analysis of English assists readers to understand human interactions in social contexts and can be used to know ideological meanings among them.

According to Mahali (2013), the systemic functional linguistics approach to discourse analysis is based on the model of “language as a social semiotic” explained in the works of Halliday. Language is used functionally, what is said depends on what someone needs to finish. In Halliday’s theory, language expresses three main kinds of meanings: *ideational*, *interpersonal*, and *textual* meanings (1985). Among them, the *ideational* meaning (the clause as representation) serves for the expression of “content” in language, that is, our experience of the real world, including the experience of our inner world. When we use language we often use it to speak of something or someone doing something. That is why the *ideational* meaning can be referred to as experiential meaning coming from the clause as representation. In constructing experiential meaning, there is one major system of grammatical choice involved: the system of transitivity or process type. I have chosen transitivity because of all the grammatical aspects analysed, it produces the useful data on the text.

According to Halliday, in his *An Introduction to Functional Grammar*, he identifies transitivity as follows: A fundamental property of language is that it enables human beings to build a mental picture of reality, to make sense of their experience of what goes on around them and inside them. Our most powerful conception of reality is that it consists of “goings-on”: of doing, happening, feeling, being. These are sorted out in the semantic system of language, and expressed through the grammar of the clause. This is the system of transitivity. Transitivity specifies the different types of processes that are known in the language and the structures by which they are expressed (1985, p. 101). The theoretical framework of transitivity was established and developed by Halliday. Transitivity generally refers to how it represents the meaning in clauses; transitivity patterns can show the certain worldview “framed by the authorial ideology” in a literary text (Fowler, 1986, p. 138).

Hasan claims that transitivity is concerned with a coding of the goings on who does what in relation to whom/what, where, when, how, and why. Thus the analysis is in terms of some process, its participants, and the circumstances pertinent to the process – participant configuration. (1988, p. 63) In other words, transitivity can show how speakers/writers encode in language their mental reflection of the world and how they account for their experience of the world around them. Halliday’s theory that transitivity is measurable will be used to study the clausal structure which is based on the main verb of the sentence. According to this theory, in transitivity different processes are distinguished according to whether they represent actions, speech, states of mind or states of being. Those are identified, classified and known as Material processes, Relational processes, Mental processes, Verbal processes and Behavioral processes. These processes can be applied to analyze news item text.

There are several researches regarding analysis of news item or newspaper as the object. NitaBonita Samosir (2012), did a research about which exist in the Jakarta Post. Nita Said that it was really interesting to analyse article in newspaper. According to mahalli (2013), in his research, there are some sub discussions which can be analyzed such us the transitivity, ideational, the rheme, logical analysis, and analysis of ideology within the text. According to fajar (2011), criticism, comments, suggestion and many other aspects existing in newspaper can may argue, attack, or try to influence the reader. He adds analysing by appraisal can make the reader understand what the ideological brings from text in news paper.

Antara News is one of the daily English newspaper which is oriented in some various field that can be analyzed in the perspective of linguistic studies using the systemic functional linguistic theory. This paper aims to analyse the news item text in Antara News entitled “*Indonesian Police Re-Examine ‘plastic’ rice*”. It includes what types of processes in the news, the dominant process type found in the news, and the dominant process type used to develop the news.

RESEARCH METHOD

The method which is used in this writing is descriptive. It describes accurately while correlating with the phenomenon which is analyzed. The data is collected from seconder data which

is obtained by library reference. It aims to analyse what types of processes, the dominant process type found in the news, and the dominant process type used to develop the news which are found in Antara news entitled “*Indonesian Police Re-Examine ‘plastic’ rice*” published on Tuesday.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The news text “*Indonesian Police Re-Examine ‘plastic’ rice*” by Anita Permata Dewi, is analyzed in the perspective of linguistic studies using the systemic functional linguistic theory. This paper elaborates six sub discussions as this study is concerned. The discussions include analysis of mood structure, analysis of transitivity, analysis of theme-rheme, analysis of logical relationship and analysis of ideology.

Transitivity in the text

Paragraph 1

Police (actor) are still examining (material process) the rice found in Bekasi (circumstance of place), West Java, recently, which is suspected to be made of synthetic materials.

Paragraph 2

"Yesterday (circumstance), we (actor) took (material process) a rice sample from Sucofindo. We checked (material process) it again at the police and BPOM (*Food and Drug Control Agency*) laboratories," national police chief General Badrodin Haiti (sayer) said (verbal process) here on Tuesday (circumstance).

Paragraph 3

Haiti pledged (verbal process) that the police would publicly announce (verbal process) the results of the tests immediately. "We (actor) will make (material process) them known to the public," he said.

Paragraph 4

He noted (material process) that if it was confirmed that the rice contained (relational process) plastic elements, the police would investigate (mental process) its origin.

Paragraph 5

In dealing with the problem, Haiti (sayer) said (verbal process) the police (addressee) would continue (material process) to coordinate with the Ministry of Trade and BPOM.

Paragraph 6

The case of "plastic rice" emerged after a resident of Bekasi, Dewi Septiani, discovered (mental process) the rice she had cooked (material process) contained strange particles.

Paragraph 7

She then sought (material process) information about the rice on the Internet and later shared (mental process) her suspicions that the rice contained (relational process) PVC materials on various social media platforms, appealing to people to be careful when buying rice.

Paragraph 8

China (participant) has proposed (mental process) an exchange of lab test results for the plastic rice to confirm (verbal process) the rices country of origin (verbiage).

Paragraph 9

"There must be detailed proof that the synthetic rice found in Indonesia is from China," Chinas Deputy Director General of General Administration of Quality Supervision, Inspection and Quarantine (AQSIQ) Bi Kexin was quoted as saying (verbal process) by Indonesias Trade Attache Dandy Iswara, here on Monday (circumstance).

Paragraph 10

According to the Indonesian government, no rice has been imported from any country, including China.

Paragraph 11

However, data from Chinas Customs and Excise office showed that China (actor) had exported (material process) rice worth US\$182 thousand to Indonesia during January-March 2015 (circumstance of time).

Paragraph 12

The Indonesian governments representatives in China (participant) held (material process) a closed-door meeting with the officials of AQSIQ (recipient) to discuss the plastic rice found in Indonesia, which is believed (mental process) to have been imported from China.

Paragraph 13

Kexin (sayer) asserted (verbal process) that there is no plastic rice in his country. Even if it did exist, he said, it would be expensive and, therefore, not profitable.

Paragraph 14

Indonesia should prove that the plastic rice came from China, he (actor) added stating (verbal process), "We are (relational process) ready to exchange the results of the lab tests."

Below is the table of the analysis above about process existing in the news, they are material, mental, relational, verbal that shows the number.

Table 2. Proses Existing in the news
Transitivity In The text

Material Process	Mental Process	Relational Process	Verbal Process	Behavioral Process	Existential Process	Total
8	6	2	6	0	0	22
36%	27%	9%	27%	-	-	100%

Analysis of transitivity The analysis of transitivity found that the text employs uses types of processes within the structure of transitivity with the sequence initiating from the highest to the lowest as follows: the material process (8); the verbal process (6); the mental process (6), and the relational process (2).

Analysis of Mood Structure

Modality refers to a speaker's attitudes towards or opinion about the truth of a proposition expressed by a sentence. It also expands to their attitude towards the situation or event described by a sentence. News item normally exists in newspaper and it consists main events, explanation and comments from the Participants joining in the sequence of happenings. The aim of news item text is to give information to the readers/viewers about events of the day, which deserve to be newsworthy or necessary. in this case, it is regarding the attitude of the police of Indonesia "police are still examining the rice found in Bekasi, west java, recently , which is suspected to be made of synthetic materials. The analysis of mood in particular refers to the mood system. It was found that the mood structure in the text "*Indonesian Police Re-Examine 'plastic' rice*" is made up of *mood* and *residue*. The moods are subject (S) and predicate (P), and the elements of residue is made up of complement or object and circumstance. As far as the modality system is concerned, it has been found that the text has one type of modality. It is Indicative Mood. Based on the mood analysis, it figures out that the mood system of the text is made up of declarative mood. Thus, the declarative mood is most dominantly used in the text

Analysis of text structure (Theme-Rheme)

According to Mahalli (2013), the textual function refers to the fact that language has mechanisms to make any stretch of spoken or written discourse into a coherent and unified text and make a living passage different from a random list of sentences. The text starts with the recount of the newsworthy event in summary form, by retelling the statement of General Police Badrodin that police are still examining the rice found in Bekasi , west java, recently, which is suspected to be made of synthetic materials.

The next paragraphs explain the background of the events, by elaborating what happened (*Police check plastic rice again at the police and BPOM (Food and Drug Control Agency) laboratories. The general said here on Tuesday that the police would publicly announce the results of the tests immediately.*), to whom (*to public*) and in what circumstances (*Yesterday, exactly the day before the news published, on 25th of May 2015*).

In the other parts of the text, China has proposed an exchange of lab test results for the plastic rice to confirm the rices country of origin. It said that there must be detailed proof that the

synthetic rice found in Indonesia is from China," Chinas Deputy Director General of General Administration of Quality Supervision, Inspection and Quarantine (AQSIQ) Bi Kexin was quoted as saying by Indonesias Trade Attache Dandy Iswara, here on Monday. As far as the analysis of text as the media of communication and information, it has been identified that the participants always treat the essential things as the theme of the structure. Therefore, three types of clausal themes can be formulated as follows: *interpersonal theme*, that is, the theme of the mood structure, *ideational/topical theme*, that is, the theme in the transitivity structure and *textual theme*, that is, the theme in the text structure. The dominant types of theme in "Indonesian Police Re-Examine 'plastic' rice" is ideational, that is Unmarked Topical Theme. The other type theme found in the news item text is Textual Theme, that is the usage of conjunction in the sentences. While Interpersonal Theme i.e, the usage of model adjunct and vocative, is not found in the text "Indonesian Police Re-Examine 'plastic'".

Analysis of Logical Relationship

The analysis of logical relationship of the news item text is a unity of forms and meanings which is built by good composition of relationship. There is one syntactical logical relationships establishing in the text, that is, Hypotaxis relationship, that refers to subordinative relationship, and two semantic relationship, those are ; 1) Projection (locution) relationship in the clause ; "In dealing with the problem, Haiti said the police would continue to coordinate with the Ministry of Trade and BPOM", and 2) Expansion relationship (enhancement) in the clause "According to the Indonesian government, no rice has been imported from any country (can be more than one country), including China."

Analysis of Ideology

The news item text entitled "Indonesian Police Re-Examine 'plastic' rice" is text which is bound to ideology. Furthermore, it is bound to situational and cultural context, it is also bound to ideological context. The ideology of the text is featured by the field, the participants and the mode. They are related to each other in such a way that they are unified. The most dominant is the role of general police chief, Badrodin Haiti. It is about checking whether the rice in Bekasi contained plastic. This is the authority of police and BPOM (Food and Drug Control Agency) laboratories to secure and to save rice. Thus it is the domain of the police who has the responsibility to guard the law enforcement and the stability of security in this country, particularly regarding the permission of imported regulation, if it proves that there is plastic rice. The text is also talking about the conflict of ideology between Indonesia and China. Rice imported from china is indicated contained synthetic materials. Badrodin state that after re-examining the rice, the result of test would be published to people soon. But According to the Indonesian government, no rice has been imported from any country, including China. However, data from Chinas Customs and Excise office showed that China had exported rice worth US\$182 thousand to Indonesia during January-March 2015. Chinas Deputy Director General of General Administration of Quality Supervision, Inspection and Quarantine (AQSIQ) Bi Kexin asserted that there is no plastic rice in his country. Even if it did exist, he said, it would be expensive and, therefore, not profitable. The point is that the general police chief Badrodin Haiti has the power regarding the regulation but the deputy director of AQSIQ (powerless) has no option except he (kexin) should wait the result, whether there is such synthetic material in the rice imported from his country. Kexin insisted indonesia to prove whether there is such synthetic material in the rice imported

The news item text entitled "Indonesian Police Re-Examine 'plastic' rice", as a text under a particular context of situation, has a macro structure whose elements are *the field*, that is, the element which refers to what is happening; that is, the situational context of feeling to find and to guard. The other side, china has to wait the result of the test hel by the police. *the participants (tenor)*, that is, the element which refers to those who are directly and indirectly involved in the text; , those are 1) the general police chief, Badrodin Haiti, 2) Chinas Deputy Director General of General Administration of Quality Supervision, Inspection and Quarantine (AQSIQ) Bi Kexin, 3) BPOM, and 4) Dewi Septiani. and *the mode* , that is, the language elements used as the communication media, the text is delivered in the written form.

In the context of culture, The news item text entitled "Indonesian Police Re-Examine 'plastic' rice" is categorized as News item text, which is usually applied in newspaper and it includes main events, elaboration and comments from the participants take part in the sequence of

happenings. According to Mahalli (2013) The purpose of news item text is to give information to the readers/viewers about events of the day, which are considered newsworthy or important, in this case, it is about the attitude of the police and the people who must careful when buying rice.

Lexicogrammatical features of the News Item text includes short, telegraphic information are captured in headline (Gerot and Wignell 1994:200). Hopefully, by reading the headlines the readers will know the content of the news. It also uses material processes to retell the events and projects verbal processes in sources states. In addition, news item focuses on circumstances. While the language feature of news item is past tense. From the text we know how the mode – the language used as communication media by the participants (The general police chief and Cina deputy director general of AQSIIQ). They are in different level in the system. we know how the power relation takes place in the communication between the participants.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the news text “*Indonesian Police Re-Examine ‘plastic’ rice*” based on the SFL theory comprehensively analyzes mood structure, analysis of transitivity, analysis of the theme, analysis of logical relationship and analysis of ideology and context of situation and culture analysis.

Based on the results of the data analysis, from the mood point of view, the text has the structure of *MOOD* and *RESIDUE*. The mood is made up of subject (S) and predicate (P) with the structure $S \wedge P$ and the residue is made up of complement or object and circumstance. In addition, among the mood forms used in the text, the declarative sentence is the most dominant. It has also been found that, as far as its modality category is concerned, it only has indicative mood type.

From the analysis of macro transitivity, it can be concluded that the processes taking place in it can be formulated from the highest to the lowest such as the : the material process (8); the verbal process (6); the mental process (6), and the relational process (2). Then, as far as the theme analysis is concerned, there are two types found in the text, those are ; ideational, that is Unmarked Topical Theme. The other type of theme found in is Textual Theme, that is the usage of conjunction in the sentences.

The reason why such themes appear is that the participants have considered them essential things in communicative context so that the message submitted is clearly acceptable to the addressee. Intra clausal, which determines logical relationship, is also found in the text as well as theme relationship. The intra clausal relationship emphasizes new and given information. There are two types of relationships. They are syntactical and semantic relationships. The syntactical logical relationship found in this text is hypotaxis relationships; in contrast, in semantic logic relationship there are two types of relationship, those are, 1) Projection (locution) and 2) expansion relationship.

From the ideological analysis of the news item text “*Indonesian Police Re-Examine ‘plastic’ rice*”, it can be concluded that the text has ideological meaning whose features can be found in the field with one or more form(s) of mood as its variant(s), in the tenor referred to, in the field and in the mode representing the ideological meaning both in the field in the tenor. The most concrete ideological feature is the conflict ; the general police chief Badrodin Haiti has the power regarding the regulation but the deputy director of AQSIIQ (powerless) has no option except he (kexin) should wait the result, whether there is such synthetic material in the rice imported from his country. Kexin insisted indonesia to prove whether there is such synthetic material in the rice imported

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